

Minimal Migration Virtual Machine (VM) Selection Algorithm in Dynamic VM Consolidation

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Abstract— Virtual machine consolidation in cloud data centers is a strategy to optimize the utilization of physical server resources. Virtual machine consolidation involves the migration of virtual machines from the overloaded and under loaded hosts. Planning the migration of virtual machines involve the decision of virtual machine selection and placement. This paper focusses on the sub problem of selecting a virtual machine to be migrated from an overloaded host. The proposed work aims at avoiding unnecessary migrations of virtual machines. The work has been implemented in cloudsim and results obtained have shown that large number of migrations has been reduced. The decrease in the number of migrations has also resulted in reduced energy consumption. Service Level Agreement (SLA) violation caused by VM migrations has also been found to be minimized. Consequently performance degradation that occurs due to migrations is also found to be reduced.

Keywords— Virtual machine consolidation, SLA violation, VM selection, VM placement

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud data centers often focus on energy efficiency. Energy efficient data centers rely on the key technology of virtualization. Virtualization technology allows multiple virtual machines to run on a single physical server. In a cloud environment where several virtual machines are run across many physical servers, few physical machines become overloaded and few become under loaded. This leads to virtual machine migrations. Virtual machine consolidation is the process of consolidating multiple virtual machines on a small number of physical servers. Hence an optimal migration plan is required which involves the selection of virtual machines to be removed from over loaded physical servers and selection of physical servers for those migrated virtual machines to be placed.

Significant number of works on VM selection can be found in the literature. Benchmark VM selection algorithms that are found in cloudsim[1] include minimum migration time policy, maximum correlation policy and minimum utilization policy. Minimum migration time policy selects VM that requires the least time to migrate to another host. This policy of VM selection reduces the overheads associated with live migration. Maximum correlation policy selects VM that is highly correlated with other virtual machines resulting in better resource utilization. Minimum utilization policy selects VM that is utilizing least amount of resources on the current host.

Priority aware VM selection algorithm[2] selects virtual machines for migration based on task priorities running on them. This priority aware algorithm has resulted in reduced energy consumption. Li et al. [3] have proposed a VM selection algorithm that selects VM based on CPU and memory usage. They have stated that the algorithm has reduced the migration time of virtual machines and improved Quality of Service(QoS).

Wang et al. [4] have proposed AUMT VM selection strategy that relies on both average CPU utilization of virtual machines and the time taken to migrate. They have concluded that their method has reduced energy consumption as well as the number of migrations. Monil et al. [5] have presented VM consolidation approach based on fuzzy logic and heuristics. They have also added VM selection based on fuzzy logic for which they consider multiple input parameters that include migration time and correlation between applications' resource usages. They consider correlation as primary metric that detects if the host is to be over loaded. This approach is predictive in nature that it avoids unnecessary migrations. They have shown that simulations have resulted in reduced energy consumption.

In the context of dynamic VM consolidation, migration of virtual machines are to be done when both overloaded and under loaded hosts are found. VM selection is required only in case of migrations done

from over loaded host. When an under loaded host is identified, finding other suitable hosts is the only major concern since all of its virtual machines are to be migrated. We propose VM selection algorithm that finds its purpose in selecting virtual machines from overloaded hosts. Number of unnecessary migrations lead to increase in energy consumption, SLA violation and performance degradation. The proposed algorithm is devised in such a way that it reduces number of migrations which eventually will reduce SLA violation and performance degradation.

II. PROPOSED WORK

The aim of the proposed work is to minimize the number of unnecessary migrations of virtual machines during virtual machine consolidation. Unnecessary migration can be defined as migration of a virtual machine onto a host that would eventually turn into an overloaded host. This will again demand few virtual machines to be selected and removed from the overloaded host. These unnecessary migrations gradually increase in number which leads to increased energy consumption. At the same time, there will be a considerable increase in SLA violation due to these excessive migrations. Performance degradation that occurs due to migrations will also grow high.

VM selection process during VM consolidation plays an important role in determining the number of migrations. When an overloaded host is found, few virtual machines are to be moved from it until the host steps out of overload. We propose Minimal Migration (2M) VM Selection algorithm that employs combined metric for selecting a VM to be removed from an overloaded host. Minimal migration VM selection algorithm combines two metrics: i) Minimum utilization as defined in [1], ii) Minimum Allocation. Minimum allocation of a VM is estimated by the amount of RAM allocated to it to the amount of RAM initially set as parameter. Both these values of all migratable virtual machines of an overloaded host are summed up and examined. The virtual machine with the minimum value is selected for migration from the overloaded host. The proposed algorithm is given below.

A. Algorithm Minimal Migration (2M) VM Selection

Input: Overloaded host H

Output: VM to be migrated, SELCTD_VM

1. SELCTD_VM = NULL
2. For all migratable VMs Mig_VM in H do
3. minval= INITIALIZE
4. val = mutil(Mig_VM) + mallocat(Mig_VM)
5. if val < minval then
6. val = minval
7. SELCTD_VM = Mig_VM
8. End if
9. End for
10. Return SELCTD_VM

The objective of the proposed two metric (2M) VM selection algorithm is to reduce energy consumption and to avoid unnecessary VM migrations. This would eventually result in reduced SLA violation and reduced performance degradation caused by VM migrations. The presented algorithm returns a VM that is suitable to be removed from overloaded host. This algorithm ensures minimum number of VM migrations. When unnecessary migrations are reduced, energy consumption is minimized. In addition to it, SLA violation is brought down and performance degradation that is triggered by migrations is also minimized.

III. PERFORMANCE METRICS

Number of migrations is the primary metric to be observed. In addition to it, energy consumption, performance degradation that is caused by migration and SLA violation are also examined. These performance metrics are defined in [1].

- Number of migrations: It is the number of VM migrations that take place during the simulation.
- ESV - Energy Consumption and SLA violation: It is the product of energy consumption and SLA violation, which is given by $E \times SLAV$.
- Performance Degradation due to Migration (PDM): Performance degrades due to migrations. This metric gives the overall performance degradation.

IV. SIMULATION SETUP

CloudSim toolkit [7] has been chosen as a simulation platform. Simulation is conducted using workload traces from CoMon project, a scalable monitoring infrastructure for PlanetLab [8]. Experiments are done with randomly selected workload as presented in [1]. The baseline VM placement algorithms THR, IQR, MAD and LRR in cloudsim are combined with proposed minimal migration (2M) selection algorithm and other baseline VM selection algorithms MMT, MU and MC. These algorithm combinations have resulted in 16 experiments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All possible combinations of VM overload detection algorithms (THR, IQR, MAD, and LRR) and VM selection algorithms (MMT, MU, MC, 2M) are simulated and the results obtained are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1. The observations from Fig. 1 are given below.

- From Fig.1 (a), in terms of ESV, it is seen that proposed MM algorithm has shown considerable results; when combined with THR algorithm, it has resulted in the least value among all other combinations.
- From Fig.1 (b), proposed algorithm has shown substantial reduction in performance degradation initiated by migrations.
- From Fig.1 (c), proposed algorithm has resulted in lesser number of migrations when compared with other algorithms.

Fig. 1 (a) Energy – SLA violation combined metric

TABLE 1
SIMULATION RESULTS

Algorithm		ESV	No. of Migrations	PDM
THR	MM	19.44	2458	0.01
	MMT	62.12	26634	0.07
	MC	127.98	24235	0.1
	MU	99.44	30188	0.06
IQR	MM	32.04	2519	0.01
	MMT	93.37	29988	0.09
	MC	164.48	28041	0.13
	MU	136.69	33476	0.09
MAD	MM	34.95	2515	0.01
	MMT	179.51	42681	0.15
	MC	238.75	37780	0.18
	MU	238.68	43933	0.14
LRR	MM	51	2548	0.01
	MMT	109.41	4477	0.02
	MC	119.54	7474	0.02
	MU	174.39	3580	0.03

Fig. 1 (b) Performance degradation caused by migration

Fig. 1 (c) No. of migrations

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, proposed two metric VM selection algorithm is presented. The algorithm has been implemented with the baseline VM placement algorithms. Experiments of all possible combinations of VM placement and VM selection algorithms are done and performance has been evaluated. The proposed 2M algorithm is found to outperform the default VM selection algorithms in terms of ESV, number of migrations, and performance degradation that occur due to migrations.

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